

Improving dimensional accuracy of three-axis CNC machine tools by virtual machining systems

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Abstract: In order to increase accuracy of 3-axis CNC machine tools, dimensional and geometrical errors can be simulated and analyzed in virtual environments. As a result, efficiency of part production can be increased in order to achieve more added values in process of part manufacturing.

Keywords: Virtual Machining, Accuracy of part production

1- Introduction

Manufacturing processes are simulated in virtual environments in order to be manufactured without the need of physical testing on the shop floor [1], [2]. As a result, the simulated system can be analyzed and modified in order to increase accuracy of part production. [3]. Dimensional accuracy of three-axis CNC machine tools can be simulated in virtual environments to be analyzed and decreased [4].

Also, tool deflection error of three-axis CNC machine tools can be simulated in virtual environments in order to be analyzed and decreased [5]. So, accuracy of part manufacturing can be increased due to analyzing and decreasing the tool deflection errors along machining paths [6].

References

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